

EARNINGS MANAGEMENT INDICATORS AND FINANCIAL REPORTING QUALITY: EVIDENCE FROM QUOTED HEALTHCARE FIRMS IN NIGERIA

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Keyword:

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Abstract: *This study evaluated the relationship that exists between earning management and financial reporting quality of healthcare firms listed in Nigeria Exchange Group. Specifically, the study examined the effect of accrual based earnings management and real earnings management on financial reporting quality. The study adopted the ex post facto research design. The population of the study consists of 8 quoted healthcare and 5 agriculture companies listed on the floor of the Nigerian Exchange Group as at 2015 to 2024 for ten (10) years period. A key finding of the study is that most forms of earnings management analyzed do not significantly affect the timeliness of financial reporting. The study also found that firm size, used as a control variable, did not significantly affect disclosure timeliness across the models. This suggests that differences in reporting speed are largely unrelated to firm size in this context and that managerial decision and sector-specific factors play a more significant role. The lack of significant effects from most earnings management proxies on timeliness underscores the complexity of financial reporting quality and suggests that timeliness may be only one dimension influenced by earnings manipulation. Hence, regulators and policymakers should consider strengthening mandatory financial disclosure requirements to ensure timely and transparent reporting. Lastly, firms themselves should undertake initiatives aimed at enhancing internal controls and financial reporting processes that minimize managerial discretion in disclosure timing.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Earnings management remains a recurring issue among firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group, posing significant concerns for stakeholders, regulators, and policymakers. This challenge is exacerbated by the country's administrative governance model, which places

heavy reliance on accounting-based indicators to enforce regulatory actions. For instance, a firm reporting net losses for three consecutive years is subject to delisting, and the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) mandates a minimum return on equity (ROE) threshold for firms seeking to raise additional capital through

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rights issues (Uwalomwa et al., 2016). These regulatory benchmarks, while designed to uphold market integrity, inadvertently create incentives for firms to manipulate reported earnings to remain compliant or attract investment. In contrast to global best practices, several Nigerian firms that would ordinarily face bankruptcy or delisting under stricter regulatory regimes in developed economies continue to operate and remain listed raising questions about the integrity and reliability of their financial statements (Ebiaghan & Emmanuel, 2018).

Further compounding the issue are corporate characteristics that influence earnings management practices. Studies such as Odokwo et al (2024) and Nwaobia et al (2019) found that firm-specific attributes including age, profitability, and size have a statistically significant negative relationship with real earnings management among listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. These findings suggest that younger, less profitable, and smaller firms are more likely to engage in earnings manipulation (Ebiaghan et al, 2017). Similarly, Akporien (2021) and other related studies emphasize the critical role of corporate governance mechanisms, particularly the audit committee, in constraining aggressive accounting practices. However, while these studies provide useful insights, they tend to focus predominantly on some sectors such as healthcare and agricultural, leaving industry-specific dynamics such as manufacturing,

banking, conglomerate, oil and gas and consumer goods underexplored (Sinebe et al, 2025).

From an academic and practical standpoint, the timeliness and quality of financial reporting have received increasing scholarly attention. A range of studies has examined how various internal and external governance mechanisms affect the promptness and reliability of financial disclosures. These include the characteristics of the audit committee (Abernathy et al., 2015; Salleh et al., 2017; Ghafran & Yasmin, 2018; Bhuiyan & D'Costa, 2020), CEO traits (Baatwah et al., 2015), audit inspections (Yuan et al., 2020), auditor industry specialization and reputation (Rusmin & Evans, 2017), religiosity (Al-Ebel et al., 2020), and even auditor narcissism (Church, 2020). However, despite the richness of this literature, there remains a dearth of empirical investigation into the relationship between earnings management and financial reporting quality within Nigeria's healthcare and agricultural of critical public interest.

Consequently, a notable gap exists in both literature and practice concerning the influence of earnings management on the quality and timeliness of financial reporting among service firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group. This gap is particularly critical given the essential role that healthcare and agricultural firms play in economic development and their reliance on transparent financial disclosures to attract investment and maintain regulatory

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compliance. Due to the intangible and often complex nature of services provided, it is imperative to examine whether these firms engage in earnings management practices to meet performance expectations or avoid regulatory penalties. Thus, this study seeks to evaluate the impact of earnings management on the quality of financial reporting specifically its timeliness among listed healthcare and agricultural firms in Nigeria. The findings are expected to provide evidence-based insights that inform policy, enhance financial disclosure practices, and strengthen stakeholder confidence in the financial reporting of service-based organizations.

This study evaluated the relationship that exists between earning management and financial reporting quality of healthcare firms listed in Nigeria Exchange Group. Specifically, the study examined the effect of accrual based earnings management and real earnings management on financial reporting quality.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Earnings management refers to the intentional manipulation of financial reports by firm management to mislead stakeholders about the actual economic performance of an organization or to derive benefits tied to financial metrics. According to Abbadi, Hijazi, and Al-Rahahleh (2016), earnings management arises when managers exploit discretion in financial reporting and transaction structuring to misrepresent financial outcomes. The practice is often motivated by contractual obligations or

the desire to meet market expectations. A common technique is accrual manipulation, which involves adjusting accounting estimates without affecting actual cash flows. This approach enables managers to present a favorable view of the firm's financial health, even in the absence of corresponding economic performance (Onuorah & Imene, 2016).

Egolum and Onodi (2021) extended this perspective by describing earnings management as management's deliberate attempt to influence reported income through specific accounting methods, the timing of revenues or expenses, and other operational strategies. For instance, delaying asset impairments or underestimating provisions for doubtful accounts are common tactics. Managers may also manipulate real activities such as production and discretionary spending to meet earnings targets practices collectively known as Real Earnings Management (REM). These real activities manipulations, unlike accrual-based methods, have direct cash flow implications and often involve deviations from normal operating practices, such as excessive inventory production or cutting back on R&D expenditures (Gill et al., 2013; Kumar & Aggarwal, 2018; Boachie & Mensah, 2022).

Real earnings management is particularly concerning because it not only distorts financial reports but may also impair the long-term operational efficiency of a firm. Shittuet al (2022) noted that real earnings management is employed to smooth income and portray stable

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profitability over time. Meanwhile, Phillips et al (2023) argue that even though such manipulation falls within the boundaries of Generally Accepted Accounting Principles (GAAP), it compromises the transparency of financial reports and is often motivated by private gains. These findings are highly relevant to the healthcare sector in Nigeria, where stakeholders depend on accurate financial information to make critical investment, lending, and regulatory decisions.

Given the prevalence of earnings management, the quality of financial reporting has become a focal point in corporate governance and investor confidence. Financial reporting is designed to communicate the financial position and performance of a firm, enabling users such as investors, creditors, and regulators to make informed decisions (IABS, 2006; 2008). The quality of these reports is paramount, especially in the healthcare sector, where public trust and policy decisions may depend on accurate disclosures. Gardi et al. (2021) emphasize that the recent global corporate scandals have brought renewed attention to the need for transparent, high-quality financial reporting.

Financial reporting quality is defined by the accuracy, completeness, and reliability of financial statements, without misleading users. Chen, Hope, Li and Wang, (2010) further explain that high-quality financial reports truthfully reflect a firm's economic performance and condition. The implication is clear: stakeholders can only make rational decisions

when financial statements are free from distortions caused by earnings management. Financial reporting quality, therefore, serves as a safeguard against manipulative practices and strengthens corporate accountability and governance.

The extent to which a financial report conveys reliable information about cash flows, profitability, and firm performance determines its usefulness. Chalaki, Dider, and Riahinezhad (2012) assert that high-quality financial reporting accurately forecasts cash flows and informs equity investment decisions. This assertion is consistent with the foundational goals outlined by the Financial Accounting Standards Board (FASB) in its 1978 Conceptual Framework. In the Nigerian context, particularly in the healthcare industry, where government oversight, donor interest, and private investment intersect, the demand for high financial reporting quality is even more critical.

Finally, timeliness is an essential qualitative attribute of financial reporting that enhances its relevance. Financial reports must be disseminated quickly enough for stakeholders to respond to the information effectively. Odjaremu and Jeroh (2019) highlight that delays in reporting reduce the usefulness of financial information and can erode investor confidence. Timely financial reporting serves as a proxy for managerial efficiency and commitment to transparency, which are indispensable in a sensitive and regulated sector

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like healthcare. According to Greuning, Scott, and Terblanche (2019), timeliness, along with relevance, reliability, comparability, and

understandability, are fundamental for assessing financial reporting quality and preventing earnings manipulation.

Source: Conceptualized by the Researcher (2025)

The theoretical framework on which this study shall be based on is the agency theory. Agency theory was developed and utilised by Jensen & Meckling (1976) in analysing the relationship between the owners of the business and the managers in a contractual relationship. The theory gives insight into the agent-principal relationship. Management (agent) in playing their role of disclosing financial information to the shareholders (owners) and other

stakeholders may give misleading information mainly due to their selfish gains. The key postulation of this theory is that rationality and wealth-seeking traits are used to describe principals and agents who are eager to make the most of their own utility functions. Agency theory is used to understand the relationships between agents and principals.

The agent represents the principal in a particular business transaction and is expected to represent the best interests of the principal without regard to self-interest. The different

interests of principals and agents may become a source of conflict, as some agents may not always act in the principal's best interests. The resulting miscommunication and disagreement may result in various problems and discord within companies. Incompatible desires may drive a wedge between each stakeholder and cause inefficiencies and financial losses. This leads to the principal-agent problem. The principal-agent problem occurs when the interests of a principal and an agent conflict. Companies should seek to minimize these situations through solid corporate policy. The agency theory has also revealed that “When the principal has enough information to assess the activities and performance of the agent, such agent will tend to act in the best interest of the principal.” As a result of this and with the prior cases of financial scandal, both local and international communities have raised many criticisms about the quality of financial reports (Orlando, 2010).

Thorough review of extant empirical studies affirmed that earnings management –financial reporting studies though abounds but reported mixed outcomes. For example, Sambora and Siahaan (2025) evidenced that leverage, profitability, and rationalization variables affect earnings management. Meanwhile, managerial ownership, poor monitoring, and audit committee factors had little effect on earnings management.

Tizaoui, Dabbou and Galleli, (2025) evidenced that that opportunistic earnings management

increases in a highly competitive market. However, in countries with high institutional quality, competition can act as an external governance mechanism. However, Yuniasara and Khomsiyah (2025) found no significant influence of financial reporting quality, ownership concentration, or their combined effect on investment efficiency.

Conversely, Sinebe (2025) reported that board size has a significant negative effect on earnings management, indicating that larger boards enhance oversight and reduce managerial opportunism. However, board independence and audit committee independence do not show significant effects, suggesting that their presence alone is insufficient to curb earnings manipulation. Leverage exhibits a weak but positive relationship with earnings management, implying that highly leveraged firms may manipulate earnings to meet financial obligations. Firm size negatively and significantly affects earnings management, reinforcing the role of regulatory scrutiny in reducing earnings manipulation. More so, Levia and Wahyudi (2025) reported that tax planning, measured by the Effective Tax Rate (ETR), does not significantly affect earnings management, indicating that tax obligations do not directly drive managerial decisions to manipulate financial reports. Similarly, profitability (ROA) shows no significant impact on earnings management. Meanwhile, Almasri (2025) evidenced that earnings management significantly impacts the sensitivity of bank

earnings to economic inflation. Furthermore, Anastase and Kasozi (2025) reported that a strong positive correlation between objectivity ($r = .940, p = 000$); professional competence ($r = .710, p = 000$); integrity ($r = .530, p = 000$); confidentiality ($r = .675^{**}, p = 000$) and quality of financial reporting respectively. Lastly, Khuong et al (2019) reported that real activity earnings management positively impacts firm performance.

3. METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the *ex post facto* research design. The population of the study consists of 8 quoted healthcare and 5 agriculture companies listed on the floor of the Nigerian Exchange Group as at 2015 to 2024 for ten (10) years period. Given that the entire population of firms that meet the study criteria is included, the

study adopts a census sampling technique. To ensure a balanced panel dataset, only companies that have been consistently listed throughout the entire study period and have the complete required data was included. Based on these criteria, a total of thirteen (13) companies form the final sample for this study. By integrating these statistical techniques, the study will derive robust insights into how earnings management influences financial reporting quality within Nigerian listed firms, thereby contributing to both academic knowledge and practical decision-making.

In other to examine whether financial reporting quality (timelines) is an outcome of earnings management, the following model:

$$FRT_{it} = a_0 + a_1ABEM_{it} + a_2FSIZE_{it} + \mu_{it} \quad \text{eq. 1}$$

$$FRT_{it} = a_0 + a_1REM_{it} + a_2FSIZE_{it} + \mu_{it} \quad \text{eq. 2}$$

Table 1: Measurement and description of variables

Variables	Proxies	Variable Codes	Measurements	Sources	APriori Expectation
DEPENDENT					
Financial Reporting Quality	Financial Reporting Timeliness	FRT	Difference in days between fiscal year-end and date of financial statement release	Uwalomwa et al. (2018); Joseph & Ahmed (2017)	N/A
INDEPENDENT					
Earnings Management	Accrual Based Earnings Management	ABEM	Modified Jones Model: discretionary accruals/total assets	Dechow et al. (1995); Asad & Usman (2019); Olaleye & Razaq (2019)	-

	Real Earnings Management	REM	Abnormal cash flow, abnormal production, and abnormal discretionary expenses (Roychowdhury, 2006)	Roychowdhury (2006); Khuong et al. (2019)	-
CONTROL					
Firm Size	Firm Size	FSIZE	Natural logarithm of total assets	David & Baba (2021); Olotu et al. (2019)	+

Source: Researcher’s Computation, 2025.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Presentation of Data

The data gathered covers a 10-year period from 2015 to 2024 for health care and agricultural firms were analyzed in Table 2.

Table 2: Summary Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
FRT	130	120.1378	71.78037	56	499
ABEM	130	-0.0465869	0.1258657	-0.3863	0.5372
REM	130	0.1751693	0.957846	-6.386005	4.44077
DISA	130	-0.09491	0.8043	-2.92162	5.149456
FSIZE	130	4.223483	0.7903998	2.4282	5.8746

Source: Researcher’s Computation, 2025.

The variable FRT has 130 observations, with a mean value of approximately 120 days. This implies that, on average, the companies in the sample take about four months after their fiscal year-end to release their financial reports. However, the standard deviation of about 71.78

days indicates considerable variability in reporting speed among firms, with the minimum and maximum values ranging from 56 to 499 days. This wide range suggests significant differences in firms’ disclosure timeliness, which can affect stakeholder

perceptions of transparency and reporting quality.

ABEM shows a mean discretionary accrual of around -0.0466, suggesting that, on average, firms in the sample tend to slightly understate their accruals. The standard deviation of 0.1259 reveals moderate variation, while the minimum and maximum observed values (-0.3863 to 0.5372) highlight the range of earnings manipulation across the firms. Negative values indicate income-reducing accruals, whereas positive values represent income-increasing accruals, reflecting diverse managerial behaviors in earnings management.

The REM variable presented a mean of approximately 0.175, with a relatively large

Table 3: Correlation Analysis

<i>Variable</i>	<i>FRT</i>	<i>ABEM</i>	<i>REM</i>	<i>FSIZE</i>
<i>FRT</i>	1.0000			
<i>ABEM</i>	0.0174	1.0000		
<i>REM</i>	0.0512	0.0180	1.0000	
<i>FSIZE</i>	0.0713	0.1146	0.0483	1.0000

Source: Researcher’s Computation, 2025.

Starting with FRT, it exhibits a very weak positive correlation with ABEM at 0.0174 and with REM at 0.0512. These low positive values suggest practically no meaningful linear relationship between how promptly firms release their financial statements and the extent of their earnings management practices.

standard deviation of 0.958, showing substantial heterogeneity in firms’ real activities manipulation such as abnormal cash flows or production. Notably, the minimum and maximum values (-6.39 to 4.44) indicate some extreme cases of deviation from normal operations, signaling strong earnings management efforts by some firms.

Finally, FSIZE, measured as the natural logarithm of total assets, shows a mean of 4.22, with a standard deviation of 0.79, representing considerable size diversity in the sample. Firm sizes range widely from about 2.43 to 5.87 on the log scale, indicating inclusion of both small and large firms in the study.

Finally, FSIZE shows weak positive correlations with most variables, including a slight positive correlation with earnings smoothing (0.1372). This suggests that larger firms may have marginally more ability or propensity to smooth earnings and manage financial disclosures effectively.

Table 4: Variance Inflation Factor

<i>Variable</i>	<i>FSIZE</i>	<i>ABEM</i>	<i>REM</i>	<i>Mean VIF</i>
<i>VIF</i>	1.04	1.02	1.01	1.02
<i>1/VIF</i>	0.957983	0.976358	0.990633	

Source: Researcher’s Computation, 2025.

Table 4 presents the VIF results for the independent variables in this study: Income IREM, DISA, FSIZE, ES, ABEM, and REM. The VIF values are all below the commonly accepted

threshold of 4, with the highest being 1.04 for FSIZE and the lowest being 1.01 for REM. The mean VIF is 1.02, indicating very low risk of multicollinearity in the model.

Table 5: Hausman Test

----Coefficients --								
-								
Model	Variable	(b)	(B)	(b-B)	S. E.	Chi	Prob>Chi	Decisio
s	s	Fixed	Rando	Differenc		2	2	n
		Effect	m	e		(2)		
			Effect					
1	ABEM	-1.775161	2.2774	-4.052561	11.4064	0.26	0.8780	Accept
					4			Random
	FSIZE	20.6684	8.69697	11.97149	23.9964			Effect
		6			7			Model
2	REM	5.186301	4.42007	0.7662292	1.75241	0.38	0.8254	Accept
			2					Random
	FSIZE	22.61925	8.860977	13.75828	23.7148			Effect
								Model

Source: Researcher’s Computation, 2025.

For all models (using variables such as ABEM, REM, along with firm size FSIZE), the p-values associated with the Chi-square statistics are well above the conventional 0.05 significance level. These p-values indicate no statistical evidence to reject the null hypothesis, guiding the research to accept the Random Effects model

over Fixed Effects as the more appropriate analytical approach.

4.3 Result

Table 5 presents the estimation results for Model I which tests the first hypothesis where FRT is the dependent variable, and ABEM is the key regressor, alongside firm size FSIZE as control.

Table 5: Results of Model I

Dependent Variable: FRT

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Symbols</i>	<i>Coefficien t</i>	<i>Std. Err.</i>	<i>t-stat.</i>	<i>p-value</i>
<i>ABEM</i>	ABEM	2.2774	47.86156	0.05	0.962
<i>FSIZE</i>	FSIZE	8.69697	12.75107	0.68	0.495
<i>C</i>	_cons	83.51241	55.23476	1.51	0.131
<i>Number of Obs.</i>					130
<i>Number of groups</i>					13
<i>Wald chi2 (2)</i>					0.48
<i>Prob > chi2</i>					0.7864

Source: Researcher’s Computation via STATA 13.0

The coefficient for ABEM is positive at 2.2774 but the very large standard error of 47.86 and resultant t-statistic of only 0.05 indicate that this effect is statistically insignificant (p-value = 0.962). This means that, based on the data and model, accrual-based earnings management does not have a statistically meaningful impact on how timely health care and agricultural firms release their financial reports. The relationship observed may be attributable to random variation rather than a true underlying effect.

FSIZE shows a positive coefficient of 8.69697, suggesting that larger firms tend to have slightly greater financial reporting timeliness. However, this effect is also not statistically significant with a p-value of 0.495. Thus, firm size similarly does not explain differences in reporting timeliness among the sampled firms in any meaningful way.

The constant term is 83.51, representing the baseline timeliness for firms when earnings management and size are zero, but it is not significant either (p = 0.131). Overall, the model’s Wald chi-square statistic of 0.48 with a p-value of 0.7864 further confirms that the joint effect of the independent variables is statistically indistinguishable from zero at conventional significance levels. This supports the acceptance of the null hypothesis that accrual-based earnings management has no significant effect on financial reporting quality as measured by timeliness in these Nigerian firms.

Table 6 presents the results of Model II, which tests the second hypothesis by examining the effect of real earnings management (REM) on financial reporting quality, measured through financial reporting timeliness (FRT). Firm size (FSIZE) is again included as a control variable to account for scale effects on disclosure behaviour.

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Table 6: Results of Model II

Dependent Variable: Financial Reporting Timeliness (FRT)

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Symbols</i>	<i>Coefficien</i> <i>t</i>	<i>Std. Err.</i>	<i>t-stat.</i>	<i>p-value</i>
<i>Real Earnings Management</i>	REM	4.420072	6.394068	0.69	0.489
<i>Firm Size</i>	FSIZE	8.860977	12.75107	0.70	0.485
<i>Constant</i>	_cons	81.93937	54.66636	1.50	0.134
<i>Number of Obs.</i>					130
<i>Number of groups</i>					13
<i>Wald chi2 (2)</i>					0.96
<i>Prob > chi2</i>					0.6195

Source: Researcher’s Computation via STATA 13.0

The coefficient estimate for REM is positive at 4.4201 but accompanied by a large standard error of 6.3941, resulting in a t-statistic of 0.69 and a p-value of 0.489. The high p-value suggests that the effect of real earnings management on financial reporting timeliness is statistically insignificant at conventional levels. Therefore, this empirical evidence supports the null hypothesis that real earnings management does not significantly influence the timeliness aspect of financial reporting among the sampled firms.

Similarly, the control variable firm size shows a positive coefficient of 8.861 but also an insignificant t-value of 0.70 and a p-value of 0.485. This indicates that firm size does not significantly explain variations in reporting timeliness within this specific context in Nigeria’s health care and agricultural sectors.

The constant term is 81.939, representing the baseline timeliness when REM and FSIZE are zero, but it is also statistically insignificant (p = 0.134), further reflecting the overall weak explanatory power of the model.

The Wald chi-square statistic of 0.96 with a p-value of 0.6195 reinforces the conclusion that the model as a whole does not provide sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis. This implies that neither real earnings management nor firm size, singly or combined, meaningfully explain differences in financial reporting timeliness in this sample.

In conclusion, based on the current statistical evidence, real earnings management practices do not significantly affect financial reporting timeliness in the studied Nigerian health care and agricultural firms, thus upholding the null hypothesis for this relationship.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary

This study investigated the relationship between various earnings management: real earnings management and financial reporting quality, proxied by financial reporting timeliness, in health care and agricultural firms listed in Nigeria. The analysis utilized a panel dataset covering a ten-year period from 2015 to 2024 and employed robust statistical techniques including descriptive analysis, correlation matrices, and panel regression models with diagnostics to ensure validity. Key findings from the descriptive statistics revealed substantial variation in earnings management behaviors and financial reporting timeliness across firms. Firms exhibited a slight tendency towards conservative earnings manipulation but showed broad heterogeneity in real activities and discretionary accruals. Earnings smoothing and income reducing earnings management practices were prevalent, albeit with varying impacts.

5.2 Conclusion

This study investigated the impact of various earnings management practices on financial

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reporting quality. A key finding of the study is that most forms of earnings management analyzed do not significantly affect the timeliness of financial reporting. The study also found that firm size, used as a control variable, did not significantly affect disclosure timeliness across the models. This suggests that differences in reporting speed are largely unrelated to firm size in this context and that managerial decision and sector-specific factors play a more significant role. The lack of significant effects from most earnings management proxies on timeliness underscores the complexity of financial reporting quality and suggests that timeliness may be only one dimension influenced by earnings manipulation. Hence, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Regulators and policymakers should consider strengthening mandatory financial disclosure requirements to ensure timely and transparent reporting.
- ii. Firms themselves should undertake initiatives aimed at enhancing internal controls and financial reporting processes that minimize managerial discretion in disclosure timing.

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